

Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Thallium(III) with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid and its Separation

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Manuscript received 1 August 1996, revised 12 May 1997, accepted 16 July 1997

A selective method has been developed for the extraction chromatographic studies of Tl^{III} with high molecular weight carboxylic acid, SRS-100 (a liquid cation exchanger) as a stationary phase on a column of silica gel. Quantitative extraction of Tl^{III} has been achieved in the pH range 5.0–6.0 from acetic acid and sodium acetate solution. The effects of variable as pH, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been studied. The exchange capacity of the exchanger has been determined. Tl^{III} has been separated from several metal ions.

Ion exchange separation of Al, Ga, In and Tl has been reported¹. Solvent extraction studies of Tl^{III} with liquid cation exchanger has also been reported². Trioctyl phosphine oxide has been used for the separation of Ga, In and Tl^{III} . Extraction chromatographic study of different metal ions with capric acid has been reported⁴, but work on Tl^{III} with synthetic liquid cation exchanger, SRS-100 is lacking. This paper presents the systematic study on extraction chromatographic behavior of Tl^{III} on silica gel column impregnated with SRS-100.

Results and Discussion

The extraction behavior of Tl^{III} with SRS-100 was studied at different pH, keeping its concentration constant. The extraction of thallium increased with increasing pH and became quantitative in the pH range 5.0–6.0. Common anions like NO_3^- and halide did not interfere in the extraction.

Stripping agents : Thallium was quantitatively stripped with 1 M HNO_3 , 0.006–0.01 M HCl , 0.5 M H_2SO_4 , 2 M $NaCl$ from the column. It was found that 0.01 M HCl gave the best stripping, hence it was preferred as eluant.

Separation Tl^{III} from binary mixtures : Tl^{III} was separated from several metal ions taken in binary mixtures by exploiting the differences in pH for extraction and also by using selective eluting agent. Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , La^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Gd^{III} and U^{VI} were not extracted at pH 5.5. In presence of the above metal ions Tl was selectively extracted and the diverse ions passed with the mobile phase in effluent. The retained thallium was eluted with 0.01 M HCl . Al^{III} , In^{III} , Ce^{IV} , Hg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} and Th^{IV} were extracted along with Tl. However, their interferences were removed by using selective stripping agents. The separation of Tl^{III} from Al, In, Ce, Hg, Pb, Bi and Th was done by passing the mixture at pH 5.5. After extraction, Tl was eluted first with 0.01 M HCl , then diverse ions were stripped, i.e. Al stripped with 1 M HNO_3 , In with 0.2 M HNO_3 etc. The separation of Tl^{III} from Fe^{III} or Zr^{IV} or Ga^{III} was done by passing the binary mixture through the column at pH 2.5, when Tl passed through with

the mobile phase, but Fe^{III} , Zr^{IV} or Ga^{III} was extracted. Later Fe^{III} was stripped with 0.1 M HCl , Zr^{IV} with 8 M HNO_3 and Ga^{III} with 1 M HNO_3 . The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—SEPARATION OF Tl^{III} FROM BINARY MIXTURES

Tl^{III} taken = 1.8 mg, column = 1.0×8.5 cm,
flow rate = 1 ml min^{-1} , stripping agent = 0.01 M HCl

Metal ion	Wt. of metal ion added mg	Wt. of metal ion recovered mg	Recovery of Tl mg	Eluent used
Mg^{II}	4.56	4.55	1.81	—
Al^{III}	4.64	4.62	1.82	1M HNO_3
Ca^{II}	8.14	8.14	1.80	—
Cr^{III}	1.23	1.21	1.82	—
Mn^{II}	2.04	2.02	1.82	—
Fe^{III}	3.02	2.98	1.84	1M HCl
Co^{II}	2.00	2.04	1.76	—
Ni^{II}	4.50	4.48	1.82	—
Zn^{II}	3.90	3.90	1.80	—
Ga^{III}	4.44	4.41	1.83	1M HNO_3
Zr^{IV}	1.43	1.42	1.81	8M HNO_3
Cd^{II}	2.31	2.30	1.81	—
In^{III}	2.38	2.39	1.79	0.2M HNO_3
La^{III}	1.76	1.78	1.78	—
Ce^{IV}	1.84	1.84	1.80	—
Nd^{III}	1.62	1.61	1.81	—
Sm^{III}	2.10	2.30	1.78	—
Gd^{III}	1.80	1.80	1.78	—
Hg^{II}	1.24	1.26	1.78	1M HNO_3
Pb^{II}	1.10	1.08	1.82	1M HNO_3
Bi^{III}	1.90	1.86	1.82	1M HNO_3
Th^{IV}	2.70	2.88	1.82	(1 : 1, v/v) 0.02M HNO_3 0.2M $NaNO_3$
UO_2^{II}	2.10	2.10	1.80	—

Average of five determinations.

Separation of thallium from multicomponent mixtures : In order to examine the possible analytical application of the proposed method, the technique was applied to separate Tl^{III} from group of elements which are commonly associated with it in ores and alloy samples. Results of

separation are given in Table 2. Elution behavior of Tl^{III} in multicomponent mixtures is given in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Separation of Tl^{III} from multicomponent mixtures: (i) Ga^{III} , Tl^{III} and In^{III} , (ii) Ga^{III} , Tl^{III} , In^{III} and Al^{III} and (iii) UO_2^{II} , Tl^{III} , Hg^{II} and Zr^{IV} .

Fig. 2. Separation of Tl^{III} from multicomponent mixtures: (i) Tl^{III} , In^{III} , Th^{IV} and Ce^{IV} and (ii) Tl^{III} , In^{III} , Th^{IV} and Pb^{II} .

Conclusion: The separation achieved in most of the cases are quantitative and the errors within admissible range. The method is simple, rapid and selective.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Tl^{III} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Tl^{III} taken = 1.8 mg, column = 1.0×8.5 cm,
flow rate = 1 ml min^{-1} , pH = 5.5

Sl. no.	Cations	Wt. added mg	Wt. recovered mg	Relative error %	Eluent used	Eluent Vol.(no.)
1.	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.78	-1.12	0.01M HCl	40
	In^{III}	2.40	2.41	+0.41	0.20M HNO_3	30
	Al^{III}	4.64	4.62	-0.43	1M HNO_3	30
2.*	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.82	+1.09	—	—
	Fe^{III}	3.04	3.02	-0.65	0.10M HCl	30
	Zr^{IV}	1.43	1.42	-0.70	8M HNO_3	30
	La^{III}	1.78	1.78	0.00	—	—
3.	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.81	+0.55	0.01M HCl	40
	Th^{IV}	2.74	2.72	-0.73	(1:1, v/v) 0.2M HNO_3	60
					0.2M $NaNO_3$	
					1M HNO_3	
4.*	Ga^{III}	4.40	4.40	0.00	1M HNO_3	20
	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.78	-1.12	0.01M HCl	40
	In^{III}	2.38	2.40	+0.83	0.20M HNO_3	30
5.*	Ga^{III}	4.44	4.42	-0.45	1M HNO_3	20
	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.79	-0.55	1M HCl	40
	In^{III}	2.38	2.36	-0.84	0.20M HNO_3	30
	Al^{III}	4.62	4.64	+0.43	1M HNO_3	30
6.	UO_2^{II}	2.00	1.99	-0.50	—	—
	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.80	0.00	0.01M HCl	40
	Hg^{II}	1.24	1.26	+1.5	1M HNO_3	30
	Zr^{IV}	1.43	1.41	-1.4	8M HNO_3	20
7.	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.81	+0.55	0.01M HCl	40
	In^{III}	2.40	2.42	+0.82	0.15M HNO_3	50
	Th^{IV}	2.72	2.70	-0.74	(1:1, v/v) 0.2M HNO_3	60
					0.2M HNO_3	
8.	Ce^{IV}	3.64	3.62	-6.54	1M H_2SO_4	30
	Tl^{III}	1.80	1.79	-0.55	0.01M HCl	40
	In^{III}	2.38	2.40	+0.83	0.15M HNO_3	50
	Th^{IV}	2.70	2.69	-0.37	(1:1, v/v) 0.2M HNO_3	60
				0.2M $NaNO_3$		
	Pb^{II}	1.10	1.08	-1.8	1M HNO_3	20

*pH = 2.5. Average of five determinations.

Experimental

An ECIL 5652A pH meter with combined glass electrode, a hot-cum-cold bath (Dimmerstat 70-IE) and chromatographic column (1.0×8.5 cm) of borosil glass were used.

The liquid cation exchanger, SRS-100 (Shell-Chemical), a high molecular weight synthetic monocarboxylic acid (C_{15} - C_{16}) was used as such. A stock solution of Tl^{III} (3.7 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving $Tl(NO_3)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (A.R.) in demineralized water and standardized complexometrically with EDTA⁵ using xylenol orange as indicator. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from 0.2M acetic acid and 0.2M ammonium acetate solution in proper ratio; lower pH values were adjusted with 0.2M chloroacetic acid. All chemicals were of analytical grade (B.D.H./E. Merck).

Ion-exchange material: Silica gel (30-120 mesh, B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to vapor of dimethyldichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere⁶. 1 ml of dimethyldichlorosilane was adequate for 10 g silica gel and

1 g of hydrophobic gel can take up about 0.7 ml of SRS-100. For column work, 2.5 g coated silica was poured into the column. Each column was found usable for at least 20 cycles without any loss of extraction capacity.

The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was determined at different temperatures by measuring the number of milligram equivalent of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in hydrogen form⁷, and it was found to be 1.48–1.66 meg of H⁺/g in the temperature range 25–60°.

General extraction procedure : An aqueous solution containing Th^{III} (2.68 mg ml⁻¹) was mixed with acetic acid and ammonium acetate buffer solution and its pH adjusted to 5.0. The solution was passed through silica gel column coated with SRS-100 at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. pH of the exchanger bed was adjusted to 5.0 before passing the metal ion solution in each operation. After extraction, Th^{III} was eluted with mineral acid and its amount in each fraction (5 or 10 ml) was determined complexometrically.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.K.S.) gratefully acknowledges the facilities provided by Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati.

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